

Notes on amphibians and reptiles from western Panama

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Abstract. Panama is a hotspot of amphibian and reptile diversity and many areas of the country still remain underexplored. Here we present results of our field work carried out through several years in western Panama, further increasing the numbers of amphibian and reptile species known from the country. We provide the first country records for *Smilisca manisorum* and *Lepidophyma reticulatum*. Additionally, we extend the known distributional ranges of *Pristimantis taeniatus*, *Pleurodema brachyops*, *Leptodactylus fuscus*, *Bachia blairi*, *Basiliscus plumifrons*, *Anolis auratus*, *A. capito*, *A. cryptolimifrons*, *A. humilis*, *A. kemptoni*, *A. pseudopachypus*, *Geophis godmani*, *Mastigodryas pleei*, and *Bothriechis supraciliaris*.

Keywords. Amphibia, distribution, new record, herpetofauna, Panama, Reptilia

Introduction

The herpetofauna of Panama has been studied in various areas, with most work concentrated in central Panama (Ibáñez et al., 2001; Crawford et al. 2010; Voyles et al., 2018). However, there are notable surveys since the mid-nineteenth century that were carried out in western Panama (e.g., Dunn, 1924, 1940, 1947; Slevin, 1942; Myers and Duellman, 1982; see summaries in Ibáñez et al., 2001; Lotzkat, 2014; Hertz, 2015), and the recent contributions of different authors with new species and new records for Panama (e.g., Köhler et al., 2007, 2008, 2010; Poe and Ibáñez 2007; Jaramillo et al., 2008; Ponce et al., 2008; Dwyer and Perez, 2009; Lotzkat et al., 2010b, 2011, 2012a, c, 2013, 2014, 2016; Hertz et al., 2011, 2012a, 2012b, 2013; Lotzkat, 2014; Hertz, 2015; Batista et al., 2012, 2014, 2015; Dwyer and

van den Burg, 2012). Despite these manifold novelties, the amount of herpetological exploration in western Panama is still unsatisfactory (Köhler et al., 2008; Lotzkat, 2014; Hertz, 2015).

The aim of this paper is to provide new records of amphibians and reptiles from western Panama, as a result of our surveys in the region from 2004 to 2012. We include two new country records for Panama, and 14 distribution extensions.

Methods.—Specimens were collected at different localities in western Panama (Fig. 1, Appendix I) between 2004 and 2012. The search of specimens included visual encounters and opportunistic surveys (Heyer et al., 2014). Detailed description of the habitats can be found in Lotzkat (2014) and Hertz (2015). All specimens were measured with precision callipers (nearest 0.1 mm). The report on life colouration of *Bothriechis supraciliaris* follows Smithe (1975–1981).

Specimens were deposited at the Museo de Vertebrados de la Universidad de Panamá (MVUP, Panama City), the Museo Herpetológico de Chiriquí (MHCH, Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí, David) in Panama, and at the Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut Frankfurt (SMF) in Germany.

Maps were created using ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, 2011). All coordinates are in WGS 1984 datum. Names of collectors are abbreviated as follows: Abel Batista (AB), Andreas Hertz (AH), Sebastian Lotzkat (SL) Marcos Ponce (MP), Norman Ponce (NP), Loraine Pérez (LP), Géminis Vargas (GV), Boris Sanjur (BS), and Nariño Aizpurua (NA).

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Figure 1. Generalized localities visited by the authors and mentioned in the text: 1) Progreso; 2) Aserrio de Gariché; 3) Bajo de Minas at Río Chiriquí Viejo; 4) Santa Clara; 5) N slope Cerro Pando, between Río Clarito and Río Changena; 6) Las Tablas; 7) Sendero El Pianista; 8) Sendero Los Quetzales; 9) Río Macho de Monte; 10) Cabecera de Cochea; 11) Palmira; 12) Coquito; 13) Los Algarrobos; 14) Las Lomas; 15) Playa La Barqueta; 16) Querévalo; 17) UNACHI; 18) Río Chiriquí; 19) Lost and Found Ecohostel, W slope Cerro Pata de Macho is the unnumbered symbol just E; 20) Sendero Los Tucanes; 21) Celestine; 22) Río Caña Arriba; 23) Carrizal; 24) Cerro Saguí; 25) Quebrada Ardilla; 26) Río Corita; 27) Santa María district; 28) Donoso, near mouth of Río Caimito; 29) Antón.

Results and discussion

Western Panama comprises about 140 amphibian (Hertz, 2015) and more than 200 reptile species (Lotzkat, 2014). In this report we increase these numbers providing the first country records for *Smilisca manisorum* and *Lepidophyma reticulatum*. In western Panama we report *Pristimantis taeniatus*, *Pleurodema brachyops*, *Leptodactylus fuscus*, and *Mastigodryas pleei* for the first time. Additionally we extend the known distributional ranges of *Basiliscus plumifrons*, *Anolis auratus*, *A. capito*, *A. cryptolimifrons*, *A. humilis*, *A. kemptoni*, *A. pseudopachypus*, *Geophis godmani* in the country, and include further notes for *Bothriechis supraciliaris* and *Bachia blairi*. Most of the collected specimens are now part of the Museo Herpetológico de Chiriquí, a collection recently established in Western

Panama, to serve as the the scientific herpetological reference in the region. We detail the new records as follow:

AMPHIBIA: ANURA

Hylidae

Smilisca manisorum (Taylor, 1954)

Masked Tree Frog, *Rana arborea* Mexicana.

Specimens examined.—Bocas del Toro: Las Tablas, Changuinola (9.54511°N, 82.74294°W), 25 m a.s.l.; 5 December 2005; MP; MVUP 1962 (female).

Distribution.—The current distribution of *Smilisca manisorum* is from northeastern Honduras to eastern Costa Rica (McCranie 2017). Although *S. manisorum* was reported to occur in Panama by Köhler (2011), no

voucher specimen was associated to this record. Here we extend the known range of distribution ca. 21 km SE from Suretka, Limón, Costa Rica (9.56831°N, 82.93414°W, 61 m a.s.l.; Duellman, 2001). The little range extension presented here is not surprising in view of the species' wide distribution across Central America and the similarities of environments between Suretka and Las Tablas.

Leiuperidae

Pleurodema brachyops Cope, 1869 "1868"

Colombian Four-eyed Frog, Sapito lipón (Fig. 2A).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Chiriquí river, ca. 2.4 km SW of the Pan-American highway (8.39268°N, 82.36189°W), 10 m elev.; 2 April 2010; AB; MHCH 1621–23. Las Lomas, David District, 300 m S of the Pan-American Highway (8.42403°N, 82.37769°W), 58 m elev. (no voucher specimen, but photographed).

Distribution.—The Four-eyed Frog is distributed from northern Brazil to Panama (Köhler, 2011). In Panama, it has been reported to occur in the Pacific lowland dry forest in the provinces of Panama, Coclé, Herrera, and Los Santos (Young et al., 1999; Jaramillo et al., 2010; Köhler, 2011). Here we extend the distributional record ca. 152 km to the west from Montijo District, Veraguas Province, Panama (8.018°N, 81.0524°W), 15 m elev., where a specimen (KUH 115341, ML194197) was collected and recorded by W. Duellman 3.4 km N of Montijo (<https://macaulaylibrary.org/asset/194197>).

Natural History notes.—The specimens (MHCH 1621–23) were collected in a cropland area by the riverside during the end of the dry season. The species appeared abundant; in a short walk of 200 m we saw 45 individuals sitting on the dry ground, probably waiting for the first rains of the season to breed (Staton and Dixon, 1977). Two days after these observations, heavy rains started the rainy season of that year (ETESA, 2010).

Leptodactylidae

Leptodactylus fuscus (Schneider, 1799)

Lineated Frog, *Rana lineata* (Fig. 2B).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Querévalo, Alanje district (8.38886°N, 82.51172°W), 27 m elev.; August 2004; AB, GV and MP; MHCH 295–96. Guayabal, Las Lomas (8.47025°N, 82.36128°W), 90 m elev.; 18 July 2010; AB; no voucher specimen (but call was heard).

Playa la Barqueta Agrícola, Alanje district (8.30673°N, 82.57851°W), 5 m elev.; 18 June 2012; AB; no voucher specimen (but call was heard). Progreso, Barú, ca. 11 km S of Paso Canoas (8.42687°N, 82.80761°W), 23 m elev.; AB; no voucher specimen (but call was heard). Coquito, David (8.47942°N, 82.47942°W), 53 m elev.; 20 June 2011; MHCH 2963 (field number: AB 04).

Distribution.—This species is well known in South America from east of the Andes. In Panama is known to occur in the Pacific lowland dry forest in Panama, Coclé, and Herrera provinces (Young et al., 1999; Jaramillo et al., 2010; Köhler, 2011). Here we extend the distributional record ca. 206 km to the west from Santa Maria District, Herrera Province, Panama (Wynn and Heyer, 2001), to Querévalo (MHCH 295–96).

Natural History notes.—The specimens were collected from a temporary pond 15 m from the David-Querévalo road.

Strabomantidae

Pristimantis taeniatus (Boulenger, 1912)

Banded Robber Frog, *Rana* de lluvia bandeada.

Specimens examined.—Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé: Carrizal, Corregimiento de Cascabel, Mironó district (8.50025°N, 81.90017°W), 1100 m a.s.l.; 5 December 2001; MHCH 127. Chiriquí: Santa Clara, Corregimiento de Santa Clara, Renacimiento district (8.83296°N, 82.78255°W) 1100–1200 m a.s.l.; 14 April 2009, 09 October 2009, and 17 June 2010; AH 247, AH 248, AH 301, AH 424.

Distribution.—This species is known to occur in Colombia and into eastern Panama and is further found in central Panama east of the main Tabasará ridge (Auth, 1994; Solís et al., 2004; Hedges et al., 2008). It has recently been reported from La Palmira in southern Costa Rica (Leenders, 2016; Gómez-Hoyos et al., 2018). Our new records fill the gap in the documented distribution, with our specimen from Carrizal collected ca. 194 km W of the nearest records in Central Panamá (Coclé province), and the specimens from Santa Clara collected ca. 20 km E of the nearest record from La Palmira in Costa Rica.

Remarks.—A preliminary barcoding approach of the 16S rRNA gene showed 6–7% divergence between *Pristimantis taeniatus* from Colombia and eastern Panama compared to specimens from central and western Panama (Hertz, 2015) with Costa Rican specimens not

included. Thus, because the species' type locality lies in Colombia, populations from central Panama to the west may represent a not yet described species.

Reptilia: Squamata: Sauria

Corytophanidae

Basiliscus plumifrons (Cope, 1875)

Green Basilisk, Basilisco verde (Fig. 2F).

Specimens examined.—Colón: Coclé del Norte, Donoso district, near mouth of Río Caimito (9.00058°N, 80.67686°W), 21 m elev.; 11 June 2009; AB and MP; MHCH 766. Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé, Celestine stream (8.82236°N, 82.20408°W); 650 m elev.; AB; no voucher specimen (only photographed, see Fig. 2F) Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé, Kankintú village, Río Kricamola MHCH321 (8.84648°N, 81.81339°W).

Distribution.—To date, Panamanian published records of *B. plumifrons* were restricted to Bocas del Toro province (Young *et al.*, 1999 Köhler, 2008). Here we extend the range of distribution around 180 airline km E from Changuinola district, Bocas del Toro Province, Panama (Köhler, 2008) to Coclé del Norte, Donoso, near mouth of Río Caimito.

Dactyloidae

Anolis auratus Daudin, 1802

Grass Anole, Anolis sabanero (Fig. 2E).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Aserrío de Gariché, 200 m E of the Río Chiriquí Viejo, ca. 3.5 km N of the Pan-American highway and 1.0 km from the Costa Rican border (8.54583°N, 82.83256°W), 213 m elev.; 21 May 2012, 10:00 h; SMF 97093.

Distribution.—This species is in the grassland areas throughout its range. In Panama, the westernmost published records of this species come from around Boquete, the Jardín Botánico de la Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí (UNACHI) in David, and Los Algarrobos, all in Chiriquí province (Slevin, 1942; Köhler *et al.*, 2008; Batista and Ponce, 2011; Lotzkat and Hertz, 2011). The locality reported herein lies ca. 44 km W of the latter two localities and to our knowledge represents the westernmost precise locality for this species, which has been listed without any locality information for Costa Rica by Savage and Bolaños (2009) and subsequent authors.

Anolis cryptolimifrons Köhler and Sunyer, 2008

Slender Anole, Anolis delgado.

Specimens examined.—Bocas del Toro: Sendero El Pianista, Casa de Ancón (8.87142°N, 82.41594°W), 1005 m elev.; 10 February 2006, AB and MP, SMF 86376–79, 86388; January 2007; AB and MP, SMF 89366, 89368, 89370–71.

Distribution.—This record raises the upper elevational limit reported for the species which was previously given as 250 m elev. and extends the species' known distribution ca. 40 km to the south (Köhler and Sunyer, 2008; Jaramillo *et al.*, 2010).

Anolis kemptoni Dunn, 1940

Kempton's Anole, Anolis de Kempton.

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Parque Nacional Volcán Barú, tributary to Río Caldera below Sendero Los Quetzales near Refugio Las Rocas (8.84769°N, 82.52312°W), 2268 m elev.; 6 April 2009, AH and SL; SMF 89721. Chiriquí: Reserva Forestal La Fortuna, between Lost and Found Ecohostel (8.67462°N, 82.21958°W) and W slope Cerro Pata de Macho (8.67755°N, 82.19811°W), 1250–1752 m elev.; between June 2008 and July 2010; various collectors including Joe-Felix Bientreu, Nadim Hamad, Leonhard Stadler, AH, and SL; MHCH 2151–58 as well as SMF 89462–66, 89705–08, 91457–58.

Distribution.—The record from Sendero Los Quetzales raises the upper elevational limit reported for the species in Panama, which was previously given as 2000 m elev. (Jaramillo *et al.*, 2010). The specimen SMF 89466 was reported by Lotzkat *et al.* (2010b) to constitute the highest record of *Anolis fortunensis* Arosemena and Ibáñez, 1993, and different specimens collected or observed between the above mentioned localities were referred to *A. fortunensis* by different authors (Köhler *et al.*, 2010; Lotzkat *et al.*, 2010a, 2012b). However, closer morphological examination and DNA barcoding revealed SMF 89466 as well as the entire population between the above mentioned localities to represent *A. kemptoni* instead of *A. fortunensis* (Lotzkat *et al.*, 2014). Thus, these specimens now represent the southern- and easternmost records of *A. kemptoni*, extending this species' documented distribution ca. 27 km ESE from the nearest published localities around Boquete (Dunn, 1940; Ponce and Köhler, 2008). In consequence, the documented distribution of *A. fortunensis* is again restricted to the immediate vicinities of the Fortuna hydroelectric reservoir.

Figure 2. Selected amphibians and reptiles recorded during our surveys in western Panama. A) *Pleurodema brachyops*, MHCH 1621–23 from Río Chiriquí; B) *Leptodactylus fuscus*, MHCH 2963 from Coquito, David, Chiriquí; C–D) *Bachia blairi*, MHCH 1689 from Río Chiriquí Viejo; E) *Anolis auratus*, SMF 97093 from Aserrió de Gariché; F) *Basiliscus plumifrons*, uncollected female from Celestine stream; G–H) *Lepidophyma reticulatum*, MHCH 1670 from Río Chiriquí Viejo; I–J) *Bothriechis supraciliaris*, MVUP 1893 from Río Macho de Monte.

***Anolis pseudopachypus* Köhler, Ponce, Sunyer and Batista, 2007**

La Nevera Anole, Anolis de La Nevera.

Specimens examined.—Comarca Ngöbe-Bugle: SE slope of Cerro Saguí (also known as Cerro Ratón) above Quebrada Juglí, ca. 2.5 km N of the settlement Ratón (8.56422°N, 81.82209°W), 2033 m elev.; 8 July 2010; AH and SL; SMF 91522. Comarca Ngöbe-Bugle: E slope of Cerro Santiago, Quebrada Ardilla, ca. 2.5 km NW of Buabidí (8.49677°N, 81.72208°W), 1577 m elev.; 8 July 2010; AB, AH, SL, and MP; MHCH 2281, SMF 89751–52.

Distribution.—The record from Cerro Saguí raises the upper elevational limit for the species, which was previously reported as 1810 m elev. (Lotzkat *et al.*, 2010b). The specimens from Quebrada Ardilla constitute the easternmost record for the species, extending its documented distribution ca. 5 km E from the records around the type locality (Köhler *et al.*, 2007; Lotzkat *et al.*, 2010a, b).

Gymnophthalmidae

***Bachia blairi* (Dunn, 1940)**

Blair's Bachia, Lagartija cabeza lisa (Fig. 2C–D).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Río Chiriquí Viejo, Renacimiento (8.71628°N, 82.83305°W), 515 m elev.; 17 August 2011; MP; MHCH 1689–90.

Distribution.—This rare lizard is known from the Peninsula de Osa in Costa Rica (six specimens; McDiarmid and DeWeese, 1977), and from the holotype collected in the lowlands of nearby extreme western Panama at Puerto Armuelles (Dunn, 1940). We found two specimens of *B. blairi* (F. 2C–D) near the border between Panama and Costa Rica, in the Río Chiriquí Viejo drainage. The specimens were collected during a reservoir flooding undertaken by the hydroelectrical project of Bajo de Mina at the Río Chiriquí Viejo. This record extends the altitudinal distribution from 40 m elev. (Savage, 2002; Köhler, 2008) to 515 m elev.

Xantusiidae

***Lepidophyma reticulatum* (Taylor, 1952)**

Costa Rican Tropical Night Lizard, Lagartija nocturna de Costa Rica (Fig. 2G–H).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Río Chiriquí Viejo, Renacimiento (8.71628°N, 82.83305°W), 515 m elev.; 17 August 2011; MP; MHCH 1670–71.

Distribution.—Although the species has been regarded an endemic of Costa Rica (Bezy and Camarillo, 2002; Köhler, 2008) restricted to the Pacific versant, from the Tilarán region to the Península de Osa and San Vito de Java (Bezy and Camarillo, 2002), it is not surprising to find this species just over the border in Panama (Savage, 2002). We found six specimens of *Lepidophyma reticulatum* and collected two of them (Fig. 2G–H) at the Río Chiriquí Viejo drainage. The specimens were collected during a reservoir flooding undertaken by the hydroelectrical project of Bajo de Mina at the Río Chiriquí Viejo. This record extends the distributional range of this species into Panama, around 21.6 Km SE from San Vito, Puntarenas Province, Costa Rica.

Squamata: Serpentes

Colubridae

***Geophis godmani* Boulenger, 1894**

Yellow-bellied Wormsnake, Minadora de vientre amarillo.

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Parque Nacional Volcán Barú, Sendero Los Quetzales near Refugio Las Rocas (8.84796°N, 82.51964°W), 2354 m elev.; 7 April 2009; AH and SL; SMF 89770.

Distribution.—This record raises the upper elevational limit for the species, which was previously reported as 2200 m elev. (Solórzano, 2004; Sasa *et al.*, 2010).

***Mastigodryas pleei* (Bibron and Duméril, 1854)**

Plee's Tropical Racer, Plee's Forest Racer, Corredora de pleei.

Specimens examined.—Veraguas: Río Corita, Cañazas district (8.30033°N, 81.17494°W), 172 m elev.; 13 June 2010; AB and NP; MHCH 1637.

Distribution.—This species is distributed from northern South America to Central Panama (Montingelli and Zauer, 2011). Here we extend the distributional record ca. 59 Km to the west, from Santa Maria district, Herrera province, Panama (Montingelli and Zauer, 2011) to Río Corita, Cañazas district, which is the first record for Veraguas province.

Viperidae

***Bothriechis supraciliaris* (Taylor, 1954)**

Blotched Palm-pitviper, Eyelash pitviper, Bocaracá manchada (Fig. 2I–J).

Specimens examined.—Chiriquí: Santa Clara, Finca Ecológica of Enrique Caballero (8.83064°N, 82.78698°W and 8.83223°N, 82.78435°W), 1088 and 1130 m elev.; 16 April 2009 and 17 June 2010; AH and SL; SMF 89764 and MHCH 2301. Río Macho de Monte, Bugaba, 1.7 km E of the David-Volcán road (8.68275°N, 82.62333°W), 900 m elev.; 15 December 2004; NA; MVUP 1893. Cabecera de Cochea, Río Cochea (8.72550°N, 82.49305°W), 1090 m elev.; 13 March 2009; AH and SL; SMF 89763. Palmira, Boquete, Boris Sanjur's farm (8.67647°N, 82.45772°W), 950 m elev.; January 2005; BS; MHCH 791.

Distribution.—Previously, the species has been reported only from the Pacific southwest of Costa Rica at elevations ranging from 800 m to 1,700 m, in tropical and subtropical rainforest in the Valle del General and the Altiplano de Coto Brus, San José and Puntarenas provinces, respectively (Solórzano, 2004; Köhler, 2008) as well as from a single locality in Panama, Finca Hartmann (DeJesus, 2007). Our specimens represent the second to sixth records of *B. supraciliaris* for the country, and extend its documented distribution from Finca Hartmann (DeJesus, 2007) ca. 38 km east to Palmira (MHCH 791).

Morphological characters.—Dorsal scale rows at mid-body 21–23, supralabials 8–9, infralabials 10–11, interoculars 6–10, preoculars 2, postoculars 2–3, enlarged suboculars 1, scales between suboculars and supralabials 2, ventrals 138–148, subcaudals 46–52, cloacal scale entire. The following colour notes were taken from the Río Macho de Monte specimen (MVUP 1893, Fig. 2I–J): dorsal ground colour from Lime Green (159) to Pistachio (161); dorsal blotches Olive Green (basic) (46) with a Blackish Neutral Gray (82) reticle, each blotch bordered by Light Sky Blue (168D); head with a Cinnamon (123A) postocular stripe bordered with Blackish Neutral Gray (82); anterior half of ventral region Light Sky Blue (168D), posteriorly combined with dirty white; dirty white and Cinnamon (123A) spots present between ventral and dorsal scales; Prout's Brown (121A) present on the distal third of the tail. The colouration of the individual from Palmira (MHCH 791) fits well with this description. The adult female SMF 89763 from Cabecera de Cochea presented a light greenish blue ground colour irregularly suffused with greenish mottling on dorsal, lateral, and, increasing posteriorly, also on ventral surfaces, as well as reddish brown dorsal blotches with blackish grey mottling especially along their borders, more intensely reddish

brown ventrolateral blotches and postocular stripes partially bordered by blackish grey, and a dark reddish brown tail tip. The two juveniles from Santa Clara presented a less colourful and contrasting colouration, as evident in the colour description taken in life of SMF 89764: Dorsal ground colour Sayal Brown (223C), grading into Tawny Olive (223D) laterally, with two series of Raw Umber (223) blotches diffusely bordered by Sepia (219), partly meeting on middorsum to suggest a zig-zag pattern; head dorsally with markings of the same colour; ventral ground colour Vinaceous Pink (221C), grading into Light Russet Vinaceous (221D) towards head and finely spotted with Sepia (119); first dorsal row, tips of ventrals and second dorsal row mottled with Walnut Brown (221B) and dirty white with a suggestion of Cream Color (54); iris Beige (219D).

Remarks.—The taxonomic status of *Bothriechis schlegelii supraciliaris* (Taylor, 1954) was questioned by Wilson and Meyer (1982, 1985) and Werman (1984), the latter indicated that there was no clear morphological distinction between specimens previously assigned to *B. s. schlegelii* and *B. s. supraciliaris*. Solórzano et al. (1998), however, provided additional distributional, morphological, and Natural History information and proposed the elevation of *B. s. supraciliaris* to a full species. Savage (2002) cited the need for additional studies and did not recognize *B. supraciliaris*, but, subsequently, Campbell and Lamar (2004), Solórzano (2004), Werman (2005), Köhler (2008), and Savage and Bolaños (2009) have regarded *B. supraciliaris* as a valid taxon. Recent molecular analyses (Castoe et al., 2009; Daza et al., 2010; Townsend et al., 2013) have provided further evidence for the distinctness of *B. supraciliaris* at species level. Extensive colour variation has been reported in both *B. supraciliaris* and *B. schlegelii* (Campbell and Lamar, 2004; Solórzano, 2004; Köhler, 2008). We agree with the abovementioned authors in that *B. supraciliaris* represents a different taxon from *B. schlegelii*, as its distributional range at mid-elevations is not sympatric with that of *B. schlegelii*. The notion that *Bothriechis supraciliaris* differs from its closest relative, *B. schlegelii*, in colouration and scalation (Solórzano et al., 1998) is supported by the colouration and scalation shown by our Panamanian material. Some degree of variation in the number of ventral scales is present in the specimens from Panama, but their colour and pattern essentially agrees with that reported for *B. supraciliaris* by Solórzano et al. (1998) and Solórzano (2004).

Natural history notes.—Little is known about the Natural History of *B. supraciliaris*, other than that it is terrestrial and arboreal, crepuscular and nocturnal, and that most individuals have been found on the ground or low on trees or bushes (Solórzano *et al.*, 1998; Solórzano 2004). The specimen from Río Macho de Monte (MVUP 1893) was collected in the morning in secondary forest while lying on a rock along the Río Macho de Monte. The Palmira specimen (MHCH 791) was found 1.5 m off the ground in a coffee bush. At Cabecera de Cochea, SMF 89763 was found at 23:15 hrs. hanging from a sapling stem 0.5 m above ground in the undergrowth of gallery forest close to the Río Cochea at an air temperature of 17.7 °C and 89 % relative air humidity. At Santa Clara, the juvenile MHCH 2301 was found around 22:00 hrs. moving over the palmate leaf of a Cyclanthaceae about 2 m above ground in secondary forest. Not far away, SMF 89764 was encountered shortly after midnight about 1 m above ground on the leaf of a low tree fern less than two meters from a small stream. The juvenile was busy swallowing a *Craugastor fitzingeri* from back to front, which it regurgitated after capture.

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Appendix I. Localities visited during the surveys. Locality numbers correspond to those in the map (Fig. 1).

Locality number	Province	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	elevation [m asl]	Species	Voucher or record	Reference
1	Chiriquí	Progreso, Baru, ca. 11 km S of Paso Canoas	8.42687	-82.80761	23	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	call recording	this paper
2	Chiriquí	Aserrio de Gariche, 200 m E of the Rio Chiriqui Viejo, ca. 3.5 km N from of the Pan-American highway and 1.0 km from the Costa Rican border (8.54583 N, -82.83256 W; 213 m a.s.l.)	8.54583	-82.83256	213	<i>Norops auratus</i>	AB 474	this paper
3	Chiriquí	Rio Chiriqui Viejo, Renacimiento, Chiriqui province, Panama (8.71628N, -82.83305 W, 515 m a.s.l.)	8.71628	-82.83305	515	<i>Bachia blairi</i>	MHCH 1689	this paper
3	Chiriquí	Rio Chiriqui Viejo, Renacimiento, Chiriqui province, Panama (8.71628N, -82.83305 W, 515 m a.s.l.)	8.71628	-82.83305	515	<i>Lepidophyma reticulatum</i>	MHCH 1670	this paper
4	Chiriquí	Santa Clara: Finca Ecologica: clearing with plantain and coffee on descent to western border creek	8.83223	-82.78435	1130	<i>Bothriechis supraciliaris</i>	MHCH 2301	this paper
5	Bocas del Toro	PILA: N slope Cerro Pando, upper limit of pasture above Rio Clarito	8.99207	-82.66598	1641	<i>Norops capito</i>	SMF 91452	this paper
5	Bocas del Toro	PILA: N slope Cerro Pando, ridge between Rio Changena and Rio Clarito	8.99109	-82.67118	1752	<i>Norops humilis</i>	SMF 91474	this paper
6	Bocas del Toro	Las Tablas	9.54511	-82.74294	25	<i>Smilisca baudini</i>	MVUP 1962	this paper
7	Bocas del Toro	Sendero El Pianista, Casa de Ancon	8.87142	-82.41594	1005	<i>Norops cryptolimifrons</i>	SMF 89366	this paper
7	Bocas del Toro	Sendero El Pianista	8.84642	-82.42453	1650	<i>Pristimantis pardalis</i>	call recording	this paper
8	Chiriquí	PNVB: Sendero Los Quetzales: Refugio Las Rocas	8.84796	-82.51964	2354	<i>Geophis godmani</i>	SMF 89770	this paper
8	Chiriquí	PNVB: Sendero Los Quetzales: creek below Refugio Las Rocas	8.84769	-82.52312	2268	<i>Norops kemptoni</i>	SMF 89721	this paper
9	Chiriquí	Rio Macho de Monte, Bugaba district, Chiriqui province (8.68275 N, -82.62333 W, 900 m a.s.l.)	8.68275	-82.62333	900	<i>Bothriechis supraciliaris</i>	MVUP 1893	this paper
10	Chiriquí	Cabecera de Cochea: crossing Rio Cochea	8.72550	-82.49305	1090	<i>Bothriechis supraciliaris</i>	SMF 89763	this paper
11	Chiriquí	Palmira, Boquete district, Chiriqui province (8.67647 N, -82.45772 W, 950 m a.s.l.)	8.67647	-82.45772	950	<i>Bothriechis supraciliaris</i>	MHCH 0791	this paper
12	Chiriquí	Coquito, David	8.47942	-82.47942	53	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	AB 04	this paper
13	Chiriquí	Los Algarrobos: Casa de la Alemana	8.49591	-82.43268	141	<i>Norops auratus</i>	MHCH 2104	this paper
14	Chiriquí	Guayabal, Las Lomas	8.47025	-82.36128	90	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	call recording	this paper
15	Chiriquí	Playa La Barqueta Agricola	8.30673	-82.57851	5	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	call recording	this paper
16	Chiriquí	Querevalo	8.38886	-82.51172	27	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	MHCH 0295	this paper
16	Chiriquí	Querevalo	8.38886	-82.51172	27	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	MHCH 0296	this paper
17	Chiriquí	Jardin Botanico de la Universidad Autonoma de Chiriqui, David	8.43140	-82.44970	50	<i>Norops auratus</i>	photo record	Batista & Ponce (2011)
18	Chiriquí	Rio Chiriqui, ca. 2.4 km SW of Pan-American highway	8.39268	-82.36189	10	<i>Pleurodema brachyops</i>	MHCH 1621	this paper
18	Chiriquí	Rio Chiriqui, ca. 2.4 km SW of Pan-American highway	8.39268	-82.36189	10	<i>Pleurodema brachyops</i>	MHCH 1622	this paper
19	Chiriquí	RFLF: Lost & Found Ecohostel	8.67462	-82.21958	1250	<i>Norops kemptoni</i>	SMF 89705	this paper
20	Chiriquí	RFLF: W slope Cerro Pata de Macho: elfin forest ridge, Sendero Los Tucanes.	8.67755	-82.19811	1752	<i>Norops kemptoni</i>	SMF 89466	this paper
21	Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé	Bocas del Toro, Celestine stream (8.82236°N, -82.20408°W); 650 m elev	8.82234	-82.20408	650	<i>Basiliscus plumifrons</i>	photo record	this paper
22	Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé	Rio caña Arriba (8.87547 N, 81.67847 W; 46 m a.s.l.) Bocas del Toro province, Panama	8.87547	-81.67847	46	<i>Basiliscus plumifrons</i>	reference	Köhler (2008)
23	Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé	Carrizal	8.50025	-81.90017	1100	<i>Pristimantis taeniatus</i>	MHCH 0127	this paper
24	Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé	SE slope Cerro Sagui above Quebrada Jugli: cloud forest ridge: elfin forest	8.56422	-81.82209	2033	<i>Norops pseudopachypus</i>	SMF 91522	this paper
25	Comarca Ngöbe-Buglé	E slope Cerro Santiago: Quebrada Ardilla	8.49677	-81.72208	1577	<i>Norops pseudopachypus</i>	MHCH 2281	this paper
26	Veraguas	Rio Corita, Cañazas district, Veraguas Province, Panama (8.30033 N, -81.17494 W, 172 m a.s.l.)	8.30033	-81.17494	172	<i>Mastigodryas pleei</i>	MHCH 1637	this paper
27	Herrera	Santa Maria district, Herrera province, Panama (8.10150 N, -80.65856W, 15 m a.s.l.)	8.10150	-80.65856	15	<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i>	reference	Wynn & Heyer (2001)
27	Herrera	Santa Maria district, Herrera province, Panama (8.10150 N, -80.65856W, 15 m a.s.l.)	8.10150	-80.65856	15	<i>Mastigodryas pleei</i>	reference	Montingelli & Zauer (2011)
28	Colón	[near mouth of Rio Caimito] Coele del Norte, Donoso, Colon Province, Panama (9.00058 N, 80.67686 W; 21 m a.s.l.)	9.0006	-80.6769	21	<i>Basiliscus plumifrons</i>	MHCH 766	this paper
29	Coeléc	Anton	8.62353	-80.11792	893	<i>Pristimantis taeniatus</i>	reference	???